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Electrochem 2019

AMEND

CONTINUE

Submission ID

35

Title

Electrochemical synthesis of magnetic mesoporous Ni-Pt alloy thin films for hydrogen evolution reaction

Abstract

Hydrogen as an environmentally friendly energy vector is constantly gaining importance, and there is a high interest in finding both cost-effective and durable materials as electrocatalysts i.e. to reduce the use of Pt.

Ni-rich Ni-Pt alloy thin films are produced in a simple potentiostatic co-electrodeposition process from an aqueous solution containing Ni(II) and Pt(VI) salts. The process is micelle-assisted; i.e. an amphiphilic block copolymer is added to the bath to create porous films with a very high surface-to-volume ratio to ensure a most effective use of Ni and Pt. A variation of the deposition potential in the range from -0.6 to -1.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl results in different Ni contents ranging from 60 to 99 at%. Pores are homogeneously distributed throughout the film thickness and have a constant diameter around 10 nm.

Thorough characterisation of the thin films reveals their nanocrystallinity and single-phase structure (face-centered cubic solid solution), resulting in a good corrosion resistance and the ability to work as an electrocatalyst towards the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 . Results indicate that optimal behaviour is achieved from a synergistic combination between composition and mesoporosity. In all cases, the performance is stable and reproducible, a degradation of the surface due to the exposure in acidic media is not observed.

Another interesting property of the material is the possibility to tailor its Curie temperature by tuning the Ni/Pt ratio in the films, making the system potentially interesting for magnetic devices (e.g. recording media and MEMS).

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